

Crystal structure, thermal expansion, electrical conductivity and chemical compatibility studies of nanocrystalline $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}$)[†]

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Abstract : Nanocrystalline perovskite oxide based cathode materials $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}$) (LnSCF) has been synthesized by gel-combustion method using glycine as a fuel. The decomposition and crystallization behavior of precursor was studied by TG/DTA analysis. The detection and identification of impurities in the powders obtained after combustion was done by FTIR spectroscopy. Crystal structure, thermal expansion, electrical conductivity of composition $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}$) were studied as a function of temperature. X-Ray diffraction study shows that phase pure perovskite structure with orthorhombic symmetry is obtained after calcinations at 1173 K, except in the case of $\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (GdSCF) in which cubic phase is also present besides the orthorhombic phase. The average crystallite sizes of samples were obtained by Scherrer's equation and were found to be between 18–23 nm. Linear thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) of these cathode materials was determined by dilatometry technique. The composition $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (NdSCF) shows the lowest TEC value. The dependence of the electrical conductivity on temperature was measured from room temperature to 1173 K using four probe method. $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ shows the maximum electrical conductivity followed by $\text{Sm}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (SmSCF). Morphological analysis of the powder calcined at higher temperatures was studied by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The chemical compatibility of these cathode materials has been studied with the electrolyte material $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{Mg}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSGM) prepared by gel-combustion method.

Keywords : Perovskite oxides, cathode materials, crystal structure, electrical conductivity, thermal expansion, chemical compatibility.

1. Introduction

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are considered to be promising devices for production of electricity with high conversion efficiency. In SOFCs the chemical energy of a fuel is directly transformed into electrical energy with a high quality heat stream. But due to high manufacturing costs, fuel cell system price per produced kilowatt hour is still too high in comparison to electricity produced by conventional methods. Secondly the high operating temperature increases the start-up time and reduces the operating life of fuel cell stack. These problems can be solved to a great extent by operating the SOFCs at the interme-

mediate temperature range of 873–1073 K. The electrochemical properties of the cathode are an important factor in the intermediate temperature operation of SOFCs because the overpotential for oxygen reduction increases at lower temperatures. The catalytic properties and electronic/ionic conductivities of the electrodes have to be increased very much for the intermediate range operation of SOFCs. Optimization of the properties of all the components of the SOFCs is necessary to obtain satisfactory power outputs in this range of temperature. In the case of electrolyte this problem is solved by using the alternative electrolyte materials with a higher ionic conductivity or by

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

reducing the thickness of the electrolyte layer^{1,2}. The cathode material should have the mixed ionic and electronic conductivity. This property facilitates the reduction of oxygen on active centers on the entire surface of cathode material and the oxygen ion transport through cathode material³. Besides, the cathode materials should have high catalytic activity for oxygen reduction, chemical stability and good mechanical and chemical compatibility with electrolyte and interconnect materials.

The electrical property of lanthanum ferrite based system^{4,5} and yttrium ferrite⁶ (YFeO_3) have been studied as a cathode material for SOFCs. Sr doped NdFeO_3 has also been studied as a cathode material for SOFCs. It has been found that orthoferrites possess low electrical conductivity and high cathodic over potential⁷. The thermal expansion coefficient of orthoferrites matches with the electrolyte yttria stabilized zirconia (YSZ) and doped ceria and have chemical compatibility with YSZ. On the other hand orthocobaltites have also been studied as a cathode material with high electrical conductivity^{8,9} and catalytic activity⁷, but the TEC value of orthocobaltites does not matches with YSZ or doped ceria¹⁰ and at high temperature it reacts with YSZ electrolyte⁷. In order to optimize the properties i.e. thermal expansion and electrical conductivity of these cathode materials, Fe and Co doped ABO_3 perovskites have been studied^{11,12}. In these perovskites, A site has been substituted by Sr along with the substitution on B site with Fe or Co and their structural, thermal and electrical properties have been studied¹³. LSCF based perovskite oxides have been found to be potential candidate for cathode material in IT-SOFCs^{14,15}. The SOFCs based on composite cathode LSCF8228 ($\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$)- $\text{Ce}_{0.9}\text{Gd}_{0.1}\text{O}_{1.95}$, 50 : 50 wt% and 10 μm thick $\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{Gd}_{0.2}\text{O}_{1.9}$ electrolyte, could achieve a power density of 550 mW/cm^2 at 870 K¹⁶. SOFC with 10 μm thick $\text{Gd}_{0.1}\text{Ce}_{0.9}\text{O}_{1.95}$ electrolyte and BSCF ($\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$) cathode material, achieved a power density of 1300 mW/cm^2 at 870 K¹⁷. $\text{Sm}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ (SSC) perovskites have also been used as a cathode material and a power density over 1900 mW/cm^2 has been obtained with this cell¹⁸.

LSCF has been used as a cathode material with YSZ electrolyte and gadolinia doped ceria as an interlayer to reduce the mechanical stress at the interface^{19,20} and also to stop the undesirable reaction between LSCF cathode

and YSZ electrolyte during processing. Otherwise at high temperature, formation of non-conductive phases like $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ and SrZrO_3 takes place at the interface which reduces the cell performance to a large extent. Nanosized LSCF based cathode materials increases the electrocatalytic property and catalytic activity of cathode due to presence of high surface area²¹. At the same time nanocrystalline powders could be sintered to higher densities at relatively low temperature. Combustion synthesis technique²² is important synthesis route which can produce nanocrystalline powders easily. Nanocrystalline LSCF based cathode materials have been synthesized by gel-combustion method and its structural, thermal and electrical properties have been studied and compared with conventional LSM ($\text{La}_{0.65}\text{Sr}_{0.30}\text{MnO}_3$) cathode material²³. It has been found that by replacing lanthanum with other lanthanide elements with smaller ionic radii, reduces the reactivity of cathode material with electrolyte, improves the catalytic action and lowers the cathodic polarization²⁴⁻²⁶. In the present work perovskite oxides $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}$) have been synthesized by gel-combustion method and the effect of A-site cation in cobalt substituted rare earth ferrites on their structural, electrical and thermal expansion property as a function of temperature have been studied to evaluate their properties as a cathode material for IT-SOFCs. The composition $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ shows highest electrical conductivity and lowest TEC value. Lanthanide gallates are considered to be very promising solid electrolytes for intermediate temperature (873–1073 K) solid oxide fuel cells (IT-SOFCs) due to their high ionic conductivity at lower temperatures^{27,28} in comparison to zirconia based electrolytes. So an attempt has also been made to examine the chemical compatibility of these cathode materials with lanthanum gallate based electrolyte material prepared by gel-combustion method.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. FTIR results

The glycine-nitrate process is a self-sustaining gel-combustion method. In this method aqueous precursor solutions containing metal-nitrates and glycine are heated until they auto-ignite. Here, glycine serves dual role,

(i) in the precursor solution, glycine complexes the metal ions, thereby preventing selective precipitation and (ii) upon ignition, glycine is oxidized by nitrate ions, thereby acts as a fuel for combustion reaction. Fig. 1 shows the FTIR spectra of glycine and $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$

cm^{-1} . A broad absorption band around 3450 cm^{-1} , which are characteristics of absorbed water or hydroxyl group (O-H stretching), is absent in the Nd, Gd and Sm samples. The powders also show small peak around 1590 cm^{-1} due to carbonate ions.

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) (LnSCF) precursor prepared by gel-combustion method.

(Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) powders obtained after the combustion of respective gels at 473 K. FTIR spectra of these powders were compared with the spectra of glycine to see the completion of reaction, which shows that glycine has been almost completely used in the combustion. Only trace amount of glycine is present in the powders formed which is removed by calcinations at higher temperatures, as can be seen from the FTIR spectrum of NdSCF heated to 1173 K. Trace amount of nitrate ions was indicated by the small bands around 1030 cm^{-1} , 1400 cm^{-1} and 1750

2.2. TGA/DTA results

Fig. 2 shows the TG/DTA curve for $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ precursor obtained after combustion. In the TGA curve the weight loss takes place in three steps. In the first step loss of adsorbed water in sample takes place which is accompanied by an endothermic peak at around 423 K in the corresponding DTA plot. In the second step weight loss occurs from 453 to 833 K. This weight loss is supposed to be due to the decomposition of precursors into oxides with evolution of gases such as N_2 , O_2 , CO_2

Fig. 2. TG/DTA pattern of NdSCF precursor prepared by gel-combustion method.

and NH_3 and also due to removal of impurities such as nitrates and residual organics in the powder. This loss is accompanied by two endothermic peaks at 517 K and 808 K and one exothermic peak at 833 K in the DTA plot. In the third step weight loss takes place upto 1273 K. In this step major weight loss occurs above 1073 K. This portion contains two endothermic peaks at 1210 K and 1264 K, which is supposed to be due to removal of secondary phases and formation of phase pure perovskite oxide.

2.3. XRD results

The XRD patterns of the $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd, Sm, Gd}$) synthesized by gel-combustion method and heat treated at lower temperature 1173 K and sintering temperature 1673 K are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. These XRD patterns were analyzed by comparing with the standard PCPDF files. They were indexed to generate their lattice parameters using POWD program²⁹. All the compositions heat treated at 1173 K shows orthorhombic symmetry with space group Pbnm except $\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ in which cubic phase is also present besides the orthorhombic phase. $\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ was found to be a two phase system, one

orthorhombic and one cubic perovskite phase. The lattice parameters of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd, Sm, Gd}$) heat treated at lower temperature 1173 K are given in the Table 1. Nano-sized powders are characterized typically by line broadening of XRD patterns. The average crystallite size, d_{XRD} for the above composition after heat treatment at 1173 K and 1673 K was calculated by using the Scherrer's equation³⁰. The value of d_{XRD} was found to be 18 nm, 19 nm and 23 nm for Nd, Sm and Gd samples respectively when the samples were heat treated at 1173 K. After heat treatment at 1673 K the value of d_{XRD} increases to 27 nm, 35 nm and 44 nm for Nd, Sm and Gd samples respectively. The lattice parameters generated by using powder program for $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd, Sm, Gd}$) compositions synthesized by gel-combustion method and heat treated at 1673 K are given in Table 2. The electrolyte material $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{Mg}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSGM) (PCPDF No. 890080) prepared by gel-combustion method have orthorhombic structure with lattice parameters $a_0 = 5.5357 \text{ \AA}$, $b_0 = 5.5227 \text{ \AA}$, $c_0 = 7.8043 \text{ \AA}$ and $V_0 = 238.60 (\text{ \AA})^3$ after heat treatment at 1673 K in air.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of Ln_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3-δ} (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) (LnSCF) samples prepared by gel-combustion method and calcined at 1173 K in air (C = cubic phase, O = orthorhombic phase).

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of Ln_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3-δ} (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) (LnSCF) samples prepared by gel-combustion method and calcined at 1673 K in air (C = cubic phase, O = orthorhombic phase).

Table 1. Lattice parameters of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) prepared by gel-combustion method and heat treated at 1173 K

Composition	Structure	Lattice parameters ^a			Cell volume ^b $V (\text{\AA})^3$
		$a (\text{\AA})$	$b (\text{\AA})$	$c (\text{\AA})$	
$\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Orthorhombic	5.4081	5.5553	7.6779	230.67
$\text{Sm}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Orthorhombic	5.4403	5.4725	7.7092	229.52
$\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Orthorhombic phase	5.3531	5.5942	7.6830	230.07
$\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Cubic phase	5.4249			159.65

^a ± 0.0002, ^b ± 0.1.

Table 2. Lattice parameters of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) prepared by gel-combustion method and heat treated at 1673 K

Composition	Structure	Lattice parameters ^a			Cell volume ^b $V (\text{\AA})^3$
		$a (\text{\AA})$	$b (\text{\AA})$	$c (\text{\AA})$	
$\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Orthorhombic	5.4069	5.5473	7.6835	230.46
$\text{Sm}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Orthorhombic	5.4517	5.4668	7.7084	229.74
$\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Orthorhombic phase	5.3736	5.5871	7.6822	230.64
$\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	Cubic phase	5.4269			159.83

^a ± 0.0002, ^b ± 0.1

2.4. Thermal expansion results

The linear thermal expansion measurements of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) samples were done during heating from room temperature to 1273 K in an inert atmosphere. For thermal expansion measurements the samples were prepared in the form of pellets of 10 mm diameter at a pressure of 4000 kg cm⁻². The percent linear thermal expansion of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) samples obtained by thermo-mechanical measurements is shown in Fig. 5. In case of each sample the thermal expansion curve can be approximated to a straight line. The average linear thermal expansion coefficient for different cobalt substituted rare earth ferrites prepared by gel-combustion method has been calculated in the whole measuring temperature range and the values are shown in the Table 3. The average TEC values in low and high temperature ranges were calculated respectively. The equipment has been calibrated by NIST sapphire standard for the correctness of thermal expansion coefficient values. The temperature range for calculating TEC values has been selected in this way that it contains linear part of the curve. From the Table 3 we see that the Nd sample shows the average TEC value $13.56 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in the range of 373–1253 K which is lowest value in comparison to Sm and Gd samples. Gd

sample have intermediate TEC value ($14.14 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) while Sm sample shows the highest TEC value ($14.66 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) in the range of 373–1253 K. We see that the TEC values of these samples of cathode materials are higher than the electrolyte material LSGM ($11.61 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) (373–1273 K) prepared by gel-combustion method and ceria based electrolyte materials ($11.68 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$). This problem can be solved by mixing these cathode materials with doped ceria or LSGM material in order to make composite cathodes^{31,32}. Addition of electrolyte material in the cathode will not only reduce the TEC value but also enhance the ionic conductivity of cathode which is necessary in addition to high electronic conductivity so that it can transfer oxygen ions to the interface with the electrolyte.

2.5. Electrical conductivity measurements

Electrical conductivity measurements were carried out in the temperature interval of 300 to 1173 K using four probe method for $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) samples prepared by gel-combustion method and are shown in Fig. 6. The electrical conductivities of the samples containing different lanthanide elements show a similar variation with temperature. The conductivity increases with the increasing temperature for all composi-

Fig. 5. Thermal expansion curve for the $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) (LnSCF) samples prepared by gel-combustion method.

Table 3. Average TEC value in different temperature range for $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ materials

Ln	Temperature range (K)	Average TEC ($1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)
Nd	373–973	13.54
	373–1253	13.56
	973–1273	13.57
Sm	373–973	13.90
	373–1253	14.66
	973–1273	16.14
Gd	373–973	13.71
	373–1253	14.14
	973–1273	15.01

tions. The compositions show semiconductor behavior up to certain temperature, and beyond that, they start behaving like a metal and the electrical conductivity decreases with the further increase in the temperature. The observed electrical conductivity can be explained in the following ways : (a) electrical conductivity due to thermally activated small polarons, (b) enhanced conductivity due to charge disproportionation of B^{3+} and (c) reduction in conductivity due to the formation of oxygen vacancies.

It can be seen from the Fig. 6 that the plots are almost

linear at low temperatures. These results suggest that the conductivity mechanism is by thermally activated hopping of small polarons between the localized states B^{3+} and B^{4+} ($\text{B} = \text{Fe}$ or Co). When the divalent Sr is partially substituted for the trivalent Ln, the formation of tetravalent Co and Fe takes place. The expression for the temperature dependant electrical conductivity of the small polaron material is given by the Arrhenius relation,

$$\sigma = (A/T) \exp(-E_a/kT)$$

where, A is the pre-exponential factor, T is the absolute temperature, E_a is the activation energy for small polaron hopping and k is the Boltzmann constant. The slope and intercept of the straight lines were applied to obtain the activation energy, E_a and pre-exponential factor, A respectively. Table 4 shows the activation energy and pre-exponential factor for $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) compositions. The E_a values were calculated from linear fit of the plots. We see that the value of E_a increases with reducing lanthanide size. The Gd sample shows comparatively high value of E_a . We further see that at high temperature the plots show a negative deviation from the linearity. Thus we see that the small polaron conduction is not the dominating mechanism at higher

Fig. 6. $\log \sigma T$ vs $1000/T$ plot for $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd, Sm, Gd}$) (LnSCF) samples prepared by gel-combustion method.

Table 4. Effect of rare-earth element on the activation energy and pre-exponential factor of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ prepared by gel-combustion method

Composition	Activation energy	Pre-exponential factor	Temperature range (K)
	E_a (eV)	$A \times 10^5$ ($\text{S cm}^{-1} \text{K}$)	
$\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	0.07	5.295	330–820
$\text{Sm}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	0.08	2.048	330–935
$\text{Gd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	0.12	1.503	325–700

temperatures. The decrease in conductivity for all compounds at high temperatures is due to formation of oxygen vacancies. At high temperature, oxygen loss increases in the lattice and consequently there is decrease in the concentration and mobility of electronic carrier^{33,34}. It is supposed that the high oxygen vacancy concentration is present at high temperature which acts as a trap for electron and immobilizes the electrons randomly and thus reduces the carrier movement³⁴. Thus the electrical conductivity increases with the increasing temperature and reaches to a maximum value and then decreases due to reduced carrier movement. It is clear from the Fig. 6 that the NdSCF shows the maximum electrical conductivity and that for SmSCF is slightly lower. The electrical conductivity of GdSCF is much lower than that for NdSCF and SmSCF. All these samples were sintered at 1673 K for 10 h in air. Thus we see that the electrical conductivity decreases with ionic radii of the lanthanide cations for a given temperature. The decrease in conductivity with

smaller A-site ion can be explained by the reduction of the orbital overlap as this quantity can be considered as measure of the one-electron bandwidth^{35,36}. This is because a replacement of La^{3+} by smaller ions changes the bond angle and thus the orbital overlap and the exchange interaction³⁵. This type of behavior is also present in rare earth cobaltites, manganites and ferrites^{37–39}. However, for the composition $\text{Ln}_{0.4}\text{Sr}_{0.6}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd}$), lanthanide size dependence for electrical conductivity was not seen⁴⁰. The presence of impurity in the sample also decreases the conductivity. The conduction behavior of these ferrites is also influenced by the substitution on A-site or B-site.

2.6. SEM study

SEM micrograph of $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ samples after calcinations at 1173 K in air is given in Figs. 7, 8 and 9 for Nd, Sm and Gd samples respectively. All the

Fig. 7. SEM of NdSCF sample calcined at 1173 K for 10 h in air.

Fig. 8. SEM of SmSCF sample calcined at 1173 K for 10 h in air.

Fig. 9. SEM of GdSCF sample calcined at 1173 K for 10 h in air.

powders show approx globular shapes. The Nd, Sm and Gd samples have similar morphology. SEM also shows that agglomeration has taken place in all the samples due

to high *in situ* combustion temperature and also due to calcinations. The agglomerates can be broken by ball milling. However, the particles are fine with size around 100 nm. SEM micrograph of $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ sample after sintering at 1673 K is shown in Fig. 10. SEM micrograph shows that after sintering at 1673 K the sample has necessary porous structure which is required for a cathode material in SOFCs.

Fig. 10. SEM of NdSCF sample sintered at 1673 K for 10 h in air.

2.7. Chemical compatibility study of LnSCF with electrolyte material LSGM

Composite pellets of LSGM (prepared by gel-combustion method) and $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LnSCF) (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) were heated at 1173 K for 260 h and 1473 K for 5 h for reactivity studies. The XRD patterns of these samples after heat treatment were recorded to check the chemical compatibility and to determine the presence of any reaction products, as shown in Figs. 11, 12 and 13 respectively. The XRD pattern of physical mixture of electrolyte and cathode material is recorded for comparison. From the XRD pattern we see that the samples have good chemical compatibility at the operating temperature of 1173 K as the peaks found in the XRD pattern corresponds to LSGM and LnSCF and no shift in peaks or formation of any other phase was found. From the XRD pattern of sample heated at 1473 K we see that there is significant shift in the *d* value of the peaks which indicates that LSGM has reacted with cathode materials $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) and for-

Fig. 11. XRD pattern of LSGM + NdSCF after heat treatment at different temperatures.

Fig. 12. XRD pattern of LSGM + SmSCF after heat treatment at different temperatures.

mation of solid solution takes place between the LSGM and cathode materials $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd) and thus fabrication temperature should be kept below 1473 K. The shift in peaks is shown in figure

at $2\theta = 32.37^\circ, 46.50^\circ, 57.9^\circ$. This shift is due to contraction of the electrolyte lattice which in turn takes place due to diffusion of transition metals from the cathode into electrolyte. Similar results have been reported in the case

Fig. 13. XRD pattern of LSGM + GdSCF after heat treatment at different temperatures.

of cathode material $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ⁴¹. The perovskite structure of LSGM has the property of being flexible and can accommodate variety of cations⁴² and the high temperature boosts this diffusion and thus reaction between these materials takes place. Although a trace amount of secondary phase LaSrGaO_4 existed in the electrolyte material which was removed completely after the heat treatment with the cathode material. It is due to interaction of electrolyte material LSGM with the cathode material.

3. Experimental

3.1. Sample preparation by gel combustion process

Perovskite oxides having the general composition $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}$) were synthesized by gel-combustion method using glycine as a fuel. Metal nitrates of $\text{Nd}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (Alfa Aesar, 99.9%), $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (Alfa Aesar, 99.9%), $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (Alfa Aesar, 99.9%), $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Merck, 99.9%), $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Merck, 99%), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (Merck, 98%) and glycine (Merck, 99%) were used as starting materials. Stoichiometric amounts of metal nitrates were dissolved in distilled water to produce the transparent mixed metal-nitrate solution. Glycine ($\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), which is able to bind the metal ions and acts as a fuel in combustion reaction was then

added to the mixed metal-nitrate solution. The molar ratio of glycine to oxidant was set to 1. The transparent aqueous solution containing metal nitrates and glycine was heated on a hot plate under stirring, converted to a viscous gel due to thermal dehydration and ignited to flame at about 473 K, resulting in fine powder with evolution of large amount of gases. The large volume of gases generated during such type of auto-ignition process quickly cools the powder formed which leads to nucleation of crystallites without further growth. The ash was ground with an agate mortar and pestle and subsequently calcined at 973 K in air to eliminate residual carbon contents. The second heat treatment was done at 1173 K for 48 h. The final sintering was carried out at 1673 K for 10 h. The electrolyte material $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{Mg}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSGM) was also synthesized by gel-combustion method. Metal nitrates were used as starting materials. For chemical compatibility study electrolyte and cathode materials were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio, grinded for 1 h, compressed into cylindrical pellets using a uniaxial press and heated at 1173 K for 260 h and at 1473 K for 5 h. XRD pattern of heat treated powder mixtures were recorded for phase analysis. The compression was done to furnish maximum interfacial contact area between the two reactants and thus speed up the solid state reaction. XRD

pattern of physical mixture without heat treatment was also recorded for comparison.

3.2. Physicochemical characterization

FTIR spectra of powders prepared by different processes were recorded at room temperature using a spectrometer (FTLA, 2000, Make : ABB Ltd.) with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Pellets were prepared by compacting an intimate mixture obtained by grinding 1 mg of the substance in 100 mg of KBr. Thermal analysis was done on TG/DTA equipment (SETRAM model 92-16.18) in air from room temperature to 1373 K at a heating rate of 10 K min^{-1} against alumina as standard. Powder X-ray diffraction data for the samples were collected on a Philips X-ray Diffractometer (PW 1710) with Ni filtered Cu-K-alpha 1 radiation and using silicon as an external standard. The XRD patterns were recorded in the range of $20\text{--}80^\circ 2\theta$ in a continuous scan mode with a step width of 0.02° and at a scanning rate of $1^\circ 2\theta\text{ min}^{-1}$. The indexing of XRD patterns was done by POWD (Version 2.2) program²⁹ in order to identify the crystal structure and calculate the unit cell parameters of samples. The linear thermal expansion measurements were done on SETSYS Evolution TMA 1600 (Setaram Instrumentation, France). The DC electrical conductivity measurements were carried out using four probe method with sintered rectangular bars. Pt paste (MaTeck GmbH, Germany) was painted on the square cross-section edges of the sample and along one of the rectangular edges (separated by distance L) to form current and voltage electrodes, respectively. The sample was heat treated at 1073 K for 4 h to ensure good bonding between the electrodes and the sample. Two Pt wires attached to thin Pt foils were made to act as current contacts, and two voltage contacts were made with Pt wires connected to the voltage electrodes using Pt paste. The voltage between the two inner electrodes and the current through the sample were recorded at each temperature. The electrical conductivity σ was calculated by the equation :

$$\sigma = LI/VA,$$

where, A is the electrode area, V is voltage between the inner electrodes and I is current through the sample. Scanning Electron Microscope (JEOL JXA-8100) was used to see the grain size and consistency of the microstructure of calcined powders. SEM was operated with an acceleration voltage of 20 kV using a Tungston anode.

4. Conclusion

In the present work nanosized strontium and cobalt doped rare earth ferrites $\text{Ln}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd, Sm, Gd}$) have been synthesized by gel-combustion method. The characteristics of the samples have been studied by different physico-chemical techniques. The XRD characterization shows that the samples have average crystallite size of 18–23 nm after calcination at 1173 K. The Nd and Sm samples sintered at 1673 K showed the orthorhombic structure while the Gd sample shows cubic phase beside the orthorhombic phase. The specimen $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ shows the lowest TEC value $13.55 \times 10^{-6}\text{ K}^{-1}$ in the temperature range 373–1253 K. The DC four probe measurements showed that both $\text{Nd}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ and $\text{Sm}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ have high electrical conductivity for application as cathode materials in IT-SOFCs. It was seen that the electrical conducting properties decrease with reduction in lanthanide cation size. It was found that these cathode materials have good chemical compatibility with the electrolyte material LSGM at 1173 K but they reacts with the electrolyte material at 1473 K.

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